

PHENYLTHIOCARBAMIDES. A CONTRIBUTION TO THE STUDY OF THE
 TRIAD —N.C.S—. PART XVII. PHENYL-, *p*-CHLOROPHENYL- AND
p-TOLYL CYANAMIDES

BY B. SINGH, H. KRALL AND R. SAHASRABUDHEY

p-Chlorophenyl- and *p*-tolylcyanamides have been prepared and their chemical properties studied. Nitrous acid reacts with the cyanamides affording nitroso derivatives. Both acid and alkali hydrolyse the compounds yielding ureas as primary products.

In an earlier paper (*J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1942, 19, 343) Krall and Sahasrabudhey have already dealt with certain aspects of the chemistry of phenylcyanamide. The present communication records an extension of that work and investigations on *p*-chlorophenyl- and *p*-tolylcyanamides.

Like phenylcyanamide these derivatives can be prepared in comparable yields by the desulphurization of the corresponding thiocarbamides. The *p*-tolylcyanamide forms a monohydrate at about -5° , while all attempts at the hydration of the *p*-chloro compound have proved unsuccessful (Krall *et al.*, *loc. cit.*).

The compounds undergo polymerization to the correspondingly substituted isomelamines, but ethereal solutions, dehydrated over ignited sodium sulphate, can be stored for long periods without any appreciable change.

Unlike the cyanamide itself, which polymerizes under certain well defined conditions only (Werner, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1915, 107, 715), the phenylcyanamide and its *p*-chloro- and *p*-methyl derivatives polymerize in more varied circumstances. It appears that a positive substituent in general renders polymerization easier. At ordinary temperatures, phenylcyanamide and *p*-chlorophenylcyanamide take about one week for complete polymerization, while under comparable conditions *p*-tolylcyanamide is completely polymerized in almost half this period. Attempts at the preparation of aminocyanamide resulted in the isolation of a derivative of its dipolymer (*J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1941, 18, 225), formed evidently from the aminocyanamide which must have been the primary product but had a transitory existence only. As a first approximation therefore, the ease of polymerization of the various derivatives can be represented in the following order :

A systematic investigation of the kinetics of polymerization of the various substituted cyanamides is intended but the analytical difficulties are considerable.

Solubility of these compounds in alkali and acid indicates their amphoteric character. A sulphate and a sodium salt have been obtained from phenylcyanamide (*loc. cit.*) for which the following structures are suggested :

(I) on heating forms sulphanilic acid recalling the isomeric change of aniline sulphate. This suggests a structural analogy between the two compounds and points to the re-

activity of α -nitrogen atom in the former, as indeed is further borne out by (11) and the existence of a nitroso derivative Ph.N(NO)CN and their many reactions (*loc. cit.*). This can be explained as follows.

The phenyl and the cyano groups, both being strongly electron-attracting, induce a positive charge at the α -nitrogen atom by inductive effect, the latter to acquire the electrostatic equilibrium ejects out a proton. This behaviour recalls the similar reactivity of the hydrogen atom in benzyliyanide (Sidgwick, "Organic Chemistry of Nitrogen", Oxford University Press, p. 314) and can be represented by the following scheme.

Confirmation of this has been obtained by the determination of the dissociation constant of *p*-chlorophenylcyanamide which is found to be about 2.05×10^{-7} ; in the case of *p*-tolylecyanamide it is too small to be measured. Such behaviour is in accord with the above mechanism and also with the theory of strength of acids and bases (Watson, "Modern Theories of Organic Chemistry", Oxford University Press, 1937, pp. 33-40).

That the hydrogen of the imino group has an incipient tendency for ionization was suggested first by Sahasrabudhey in the case of phenylecyanamide. That such a tendency exists and can be augmented or suppressed by the $-I$ and $+I$ inductive effects of the adjoining groups has become apparent in these two cases.

Action of HNO₂.—Like phenylcyanamide, *p*-chlorophenyl-, and *p*-tolylecyanamides react with nitrous acid in alcoholic medium to form the nitroso derivatives :

The formation of a nitroso derivative is usually considered as an evidence for the presence of a $-\text{NH}$ -group. The formation of such compounds from above cyanamides and not from the corresponding thiocarbamides appears to us of considerable significance. The phenylthiocarbamide and its other aryl homologues, as also *S*-diarylthiocarbamides do not form nitroso derivatives. This suggests that the hydrogen of the imino group in the above cyanamides, though labile to a certain extent (*vide supra*), largely remains attached to the nitrogen; in the case of thiocarbamides, however, a conventional $-\text{NH}$ - appears to be wanting. It is known that a $\text{C}=\text{S}$ group exerts a far more powerful inductive effect than a $\text{C}=\text{O}$ group (*J. Chem. Soc.*, 1929, 1584; 1925, 1618) and presumably a $\text{C}\equiv\text{N}$ group. We suggest that a proton ejected from the imino group may find a place on the negatively charged sulphur causing tautomerism in these thioureas. Thus :

Hydrolysis.—Both acids and alkalis hydrolyse the *p*-chlorophenyl- and *p*-tolylecyanamides; the primary products being the corresponding ureas. It will be evident from the table given in the experimental part that in an alkaline medium the *p*-tolylecyanamide is more easily hydrolysed, equilibrium being reached within 15 minutes at 75% change.

In the case of *p*-chloro compound more than an hour is required for reaching a stable equilibrium when nearly 60% have hydrolysed. Besides the ureas other products of hydrolysis are mainly ammonia and cyanic acid. Hydrolysis is more rapid in an alkaline medium probably because the cyanamides are weak acids. For the same reason acid hydrolysis is slow. The fact that *p*-chlorophenylcyanamide is more resistant than the *p*-tolylecyanamide supports the above view (*vide* experimental). These results recall the various studies on the hydrolytic decompositions (by Krall *et al*) of thiocarbamides where a positive substituent is known to weaken the C^α-N bond.

EXPERIMENTAL

Preparation of p-Chlorophenyl- and p-Tolylecyanamides.—1/30th Mole of the thiocarbamide (6.21 g. of chlorophenylthiocarbamide and 5.53 g. of tolythiocarbamide) was suspended in 50 c.c. of boiling water and to this were added 50 c.c. of boiling aqueous solution containing 20.5 g. of KOH and 33 c.c. of boiling lead acetate solution containing 12.6 g. of lead acetate. The mixture was boiled for 5 minutes, cooled by surrounding with ice and filtered. Cyanamide was precipitated by the addition of a slight excess of glacial acetic acid, filtered and dried over concentrated sulphuric acid in a vacuum desiccator, yield of *p*-chlorophenylcyanamide 4.9 g. (98% of theory), m.p. 97°; M.W. 152.5; yield of *p*-tolylecyanamide 4.0 g. (91% of theory), m.p. 63°; M.W. 132.

Molecular weights were determined by cryoscopic methods and as would be apparent from the Table I no perceptible polymerization had occurred in the freshly prepared compound

TABLE I

Substance.	M.W. (found).	Method used.	Solvent.
<i>p</i> -Chlorophenylcyanamide	154, 149	Rast's	Camphor
	150	Beckman's	Nitrobenzene
<i>p</i> -Tolylecyanamide	131, 133	Rast's	Camphor
	130	Beckman's	Nitrobenzene

Hydration.—The compounds as isolated at the room temperature were found devoid of any water of hydration. When well dried samples were treated with water, cooled by a freezing mixture (−5°) a monohydrate was obtained in the case of *p*-tolylecyanamide. *p*-Chlorophenylcyanamide did not take up any water of crystallisation.

Polymerization.—These cyanamides left as such undergo polymerization to the corresponding isomelamines. In the case of *p*-tolylecyanamide, at ordinary temperatures about 2-3 days are required for complete polymerization, the chloro derivative polymerizing in about a week. At lower temperatures the polymerization proceeds more slowly, while if heated on a water-bath complete polymerization is effected within 45 minutes.

Tri-*p*-tolylisomelamine, m.p. 256°. (Found: N, 21.4. Calc. N, 21.2 per cent).

Tri-*p*-chlorophenylisomelamine, m.p. 280° (Found: N, 18.4. Calc., N, 18.3 per cent).

Action of Nitrous Acid. (In an alcoholic medium).—To 15 c.c. of a 10% solution of the cyanamide in alcohol were added 3 c.c. of concentrated hydrochloric acid. A saturated solution of sodium nitrite was then gradually added with constant stirring till effervescence ceased. Yellow nitroso derivatives separated out.

- (i) The nitroso derivative of *p*-chlorophenylcyanamide was crystallised from alcohol, m.p. 183°. (Found : N, 23.6, 23.7 ; Cl, 19.7, 19.5. $C_6H_4ON_2Cl$ requires N, 23.9 ; Cl, 19.66 per cent).
- (ii) The nitroso derivative of *p*-tolylcyanamide was crystallised from alcohol. (Found : N, 25.5. $C_8H_7ON_2$ requires N, 25.9 per cent).

Hydrolysis : Action of water, aqueous acid and alkali.—The solubility of the cyanamides under investigation is very low in water, of the order of 0.1 to 0.2%. If an aqueous

FIG. 1

solution is allowed to stand for several days isomelamines are precipitated. In boiling solutions other products also appear but were not examined. Traces of the corresponding ureas are formed (*p*-chlorophenylurea, m.p. 206° ; *p*-tolyl urea, m.p. 180°). The behaviour is comparable with phenylcyanamide. Both acids and alkalis hydrolyse these derivatives to the corresponding ureas ; isomelamines are not formed in any appreciable quantity. Other products of hydrolysis are ammonia, cyanic acid, CO_2 etc., formed probably as a result of the secondary decompositions.

Alkali Hydrolysis.—1/200th Mole of the cyanamide taken in a 100 c.c. R.B. flask with an equivalent quantity of the hydrolysing agent (5 c.c. of normal NaOH solution) was boiled under a reflux condenser for the desired period. Unchanged cyanamide was then estimated titrimetrically (*vide J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1942, 19, 343).

Acid Hydrolysis.—Preliminary experiments revealed that the acid hydrolysis is very slow as compared with alkali hydrolysis.

Time.	% Hydrolysis of <i>p</i> -chloro-phenylcyanamide.	% Hydrolysis of <i>p</i> -tolylcyanamide.
15 min.	30	71.0
45	49	75.1
60	55	75.2
75	58	75.2
120	60	75.6
180	60.5	76.0